

Synthesis of Coumarins and Chromones.

A Preliminary Note.

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It has been shown by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407) that Simoni's method of synthesis of chromones from phenols and β -ketonic esters using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent is not of general application and that polyhydroxy phenols, *viz.*, resorcinol, orcinol, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol, as also α -naphthol give coumarins even with phosphorus pentoxide. Further investigations in this direction show that only those phenols, which react with difficulty or do not react at all with β -ketonic esters using sulphuric acid to form coumarins, yield with phosphorus pentoxide chromones; while those phenols which form coumarins readily with good yield using sulphuric acid, invariably give coumarins by changing the condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide. Thus phenol, cresols, β -naphthol, halogenated phenols, nitrophenols and phenol-carboxylic acids, guaiacol and hydroquinone yield always chromones, when condensed with substituted ethyl acetoacetates (the substituents being methyl, ethyl, propyl, isopropyl, allyl, isobutyl, benzyl amyl and chloro), the yield increasing as the substituents become heavier. As these chromones contain a reactive methyl group in 2-position, they readily react with benzaldehyde to form styrene derivatives, and they are thus distinguished from the isomeric coumarins. In order to find a satisfactory explanation of the mechanism of this reaction, the condensations of resorcinol-mono- and dimethyl-ether with ethyl acetoacetates and with ethyldimethyl- (or diethyl)-acetoacetate have also been attempted in the presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide with interesting results. The details of this investigation will be communicated as soon as the analytical work is finished.

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A paper entitled "Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and ketonic Esters using Phosphorus Pentoxide. Part I. Coumarins from Resorcinol and Ethylacetoacetates" was submitted to the Indian Chemical Society by the author, D. Chakravarti, on the 9th February, 1931; whereas work on similar lines seems to have been carried on by Robertson and his collaborators, at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine and was submitted for publication to the Chemical Society, London, on the 16th March, 1931.

Since then, both Chakravarti and Robertson are simultaneously working in India and England on the same lines and are publishing their work in the Journals of the Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta (India) and the Chemical Society, London, respectively.

Editor.